

EMP-LAC

Least-Cost Electrification Analysis for the State of Acre, Brazil

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OnSSET, Brazil, Acre, electrification, LCOE, 2030, 2050, renewable energy, solar PV, mini-grids

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Executive Summary

This study applies the Open Source Spatial Electrification Toolkit (OnSSET) to identify least-cost electrification strategies for the state of Acre, Brazil. Due to computational constraints in processing the full national territory, Acre was selected as a focused case study. Two scenarios were modeled — a near-term 2030 horizon and a long-term 2050 horizon — both targeting universal (100%) electricity access.

For the 2030 scenario, approximately USD 513 million in investment is required to serve an estimated population of 965,000 (from a model input of 980,000) through

124,000 new connections with 124.5 MW of installed capacity. By 2050, total investment will increase to USD 641 million for 1,138,000 people, with 160,730 new connections and 166 MW of capacity.

In both scenarios, grid densification serves the largest population share (68-69%), while standalone solar PV systems require the highest investment share (36-41%), reflecting the high per-capita cost of electrifying dispersed Amazonian settlements. The technology mix remains solar-dominated for off-grid solutions, with wind and hydro mini-grids not selected as cost-effective options under current assumptions. Total CO₂ emissions are modest at 109 tCO₂ (2030) and 159 tCO₂ (2050), reflecting the renewable-heavy approach.

1. Introduction

Brazil is the largest country in South America, with a diverse geography that presents significant challenges for universal electrification. While the national electrification rate is high, remote regions in the Amazon basin continue to face energy access gaps. The state of Acre, located in the western Amazon bordering Peru and Bolivia, had a population of 830,018 according to the 2022 Demographic Census (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística [IBGE], 2022), with an estimated 884,372 inhabitants by 2025 (IBGE, 2024).

Despite Brazil's national electricity access rate reaching 99.8% in 2024, Acre remains one of the states with the highest electrification deficits in the Legal Amazon. Most urban areas, including the capital Rio Branco, are connected to the National Interconnected System (Sistema Interligado Nacional [SIN]), which serves approximately 98% of the national electricity market. However, many remote communities remain off-grid, dependent on diesel generators, or supplied through small isolated systems. Electrification barriers include dense Amazon rainforest terrain that complicates transmission and distribution expansion, communities accessible primarily by river, limited and seasonally unreliable road infrastructure, and very low population density at 5.06 inhabitants per km² (IBGE, 2022).

Federal programs such as Luz para Todos relaunched in 2023 after a period of discontinuity and Mais Luz para Amazônia increasingly deploy off-grid photovoltaic systems for remote Amazon communities where conventional grid extension is not economically feasible. In November 2023, the Ministry of Mines and Energy (MME) contracted 5,337 new installations for Acre under the Luz para Todos program (MME, 2023). However, implementation has faced delays: a 2025 audit by the Instituto Brasileiro de Defesa do Consumidor (Idec) reported that Acre recorded no completed connections under the program in 2024, underscoring the logistical difficulties of operating in the region. Brazil's Energy Research Company (EPE) has published

studies on isolated electricity generation in Acre indicating that declining photovoltaic equipment costs will increasingly favor solar solutions over diesel in the state's isolated systems (EPE, 2023). Acre also has relatively high rural poverty levels and vulnerable populations, including Indigenous and riverine communities, for whom limited electricity access directly affects healthcare, refrigeration, education, and local economic development.

This study addresses two research questions: (1) What is the least-cost technology mix, required investment, and installed capacity needed to achieve universal electricity access in Acre? (2) How does the optimal electrification strategy differ between a near-term (2030) and long-term (2050) planning horizon, and what are the implications for phased investment?

Due to computational constraints in processing Brazil's full territory within the OnSSET framework, Acre was selected as a focused case study. Two scenarios are analyzed: a near-term 2030 horizon and a long-term 2050 horizon, both targeting 100% electrification from a 2022 base year.

Figure 1 presents the geographic location of Acre within Brazil.

2. Methodology

The analysis employs OnSSET, an open-source GIS-based optimization tool that integrates geospatial analysis with leveled cost of electricity (LCoE) calculations to determine the least-cost electrification option for each settlement (Sahlberg et al., 2025a). Grid expansion is prioritized where cost-effective and within 80 km of the medium-voltage (MV) network. When grid connection is not feasible, the mini-grid configuration with the lowest LCoE is selected, subject to a minimum settlement size of 25 households, a minimum distance of 3 km from existing MV lines, 95% supply reliability, and a maximum diesel generation share of 25%. Standalone solar home systems (SHS) serve remaining settlements where neither grid extension nor mini-grids are viable.

GIS data acquisition and processing were carried out using QGIS (QGIS Development Team, 2024), including layer review, coordinate projection, clipping, and merging to generate the input .csv file for OnSSET. The model was executed in Python within a Jupyter Notebook environment.

Demand targets are differentiated: Tier 5 (3,000 kWh/hh/year) for urban areas, Tier 2 (73 kWh/hh/year) for large rural settlements, and Tier 3 (365 kWh/hh/year) for small rural settlements (<25 households). Productive demand is included.

2.1 Data Sources

#	Dataset	Type	Source
1	Administrative boundaries	Polygon	https://gadm.org/download_country.html
2	Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI)	Raster	https://globalsolaratlas.info/
3	Wind Speed	Raster	https://globalwindatlas.info/en/download/gis-files
4	Night-time lights	Raster	https://eogdata.mines.edu/nighttime_light/annual/v22/2025/
5	HV network (Existing)	Line shapefile	https://www.epe.gov.br/pt/publicacoes-dados-abertos/publicacoes/webmap-epe
6	HV network (Planned)	Line shapefile	https://www.epe.gov.br/pt/publicacoes-dados-abertos/publicacoes/webmap-epe
7	MV network (Existing)	Line shapefile	https://dadosabertos-aneel.opendata.arcgis.com/search?tags=distribicao
8	Population clusters	Raster	https://hub.worldpop.org/project/categories?id=3
9	Roads	Line shapefile	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0038536/brazil-road-network-federal-and-state-highways
10	Substations	Point shapefile	https://www.epe.gov.br/pt/publicacoes-

			dados-abertos/publicacoes/webmap-epe
11	Travel time	Raster	https://phys-techsciences.datastations.nl/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.17026/dans-ztx-2sd2
12	Health facilities	Point shapefile	https://data.humdata.org/
13	Education facilities	Point shapefile	https://data.humdata.org/
14	Distribution transformers	Point shapefile	https://dadosabertos-aneel.opendata.arcgis.com/search?tags=distribuicao

2.2 General Parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit
Base year	2022	–
End years	2030 / 2050	–
Electrification target	100	%
Population (2030 / 2050)	980,000 / 1,138,000	inhabitants
Urban ratio	79% (2030) / 82% (2050)	%
People per hh (urban / rural)	3.0 / 3.8	people/hh
Rural settlement cutoff	25	households
Urban demand target	Tier 5 (3,000)	kWh/hh/yr
Large rural demand	Tier 2 (73)	kWh/hh/yr
Small rural demand	Tier 3 (365)	kWh/hh/yr
Productive demand	Included	–
Diesel price	1.60	USD/liter

Table
General Model Parameters for the Acre Electrification Analysis

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2.3 Grid Parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit
Grid generation cost	0.09	USD/kWh
Grid capital cost	1,500	USD/kW
Grid losses	25	%

Grid emission factor	250	gCO ₂ /kWh
Annual connection limit	15,000	hh/yr
Annual capacity limit	150	MW/yr
HV line cost	180,000	USD/km
MV line cost	40,000	USD/km
MV max length	80	km
LV line cost	18,000	USD/km
Service transformer	75 kVA / \$9,500	kVA / USD
HV/MV transformer	15,000 kVA / \$1.1M	kVA / USD
Grid discount rate	10	%

Table
Grid Infrastructure Parameters

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2.4 Mini-Grid Parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit
PV panel cost (incl. BoS)	950	USD/kW
Battery cost	220	USD/kWh
Battery inverter	300	USD/kW
Diesel generator	550	USD/kW
Wind turbine	1,800	USD/kW
Hydro capital cost	12,000	USD/kW
PV lifetime	25	years
LPSP max	5	%
Max diesel share	25	%
Min settlement size	25	hh
Min grid distance	3	km
MG discount rate	14	%

Table
Mini-Grid Technology Parameters

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2.5 Standalone Solar PV Parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit
SA PV cost (<20 W)	10,000	USD/kW
SA PV cost (21–50 W)	7,000	USD/kW
SA PV cost (51–100 W)	3,500	USD/kW
SA PV cost (101–1,000 W)	5,500	USD/kW
SA PV cost (>1 kW)	4,000	USD/kW
SHS lifetime	6	years
Standalone discount rate	18	%

Table
Standalone Solar PV (Solar Home System) Parameters

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2.6 Scenarios

Scenario	Description	Key Assumptions
Acre 2030	Near-term scenario targeting universal access by 2030.	Pop: 980,000. Urban: 79%. 8-year horizon. Same costs & grid specs as 2050.
Acre 2050	Long-term scenario targeting universal access by 2050.	Pop: 1,138,000. Urban: 82%. 28-year horizon. Same costs & grid specs as 2030.

Table
Scenario Definitions

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3. Results

3.1 Acre – 2030 Scenario

Table 6 presents the summarized results for the 2030 scenario.

Technology	Population 2030	New Conn. 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (M USD)	Emissions 2030 (tCO ₂)
Grid_dens	655,000	30,000	27.5	48	23*
Grid_ext	115,000	30,000	27.0	170	18*
SA_PV	140,000	40,000	26.0	210	0.00
MG_PV_Hybrid	55,000	24,000	44.0	85	68*
MG_Wind	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
MG_Hydro	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Non-electrified	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00

Total	965,000	124,000	124.5	513	~109*
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Table 6
 Summary of 2030 Electrification Results for Acre
 Note. Values are approximate, derived from OnSSET model output charts. Emissions values marked with * are estimates pending verification against exact model output.

Figure 2 presents the geospatial distribution of electrification technologies across Acre for the 2030 scenario.

Figure 3
 Population, New Connections, Capacity, and Investment by Technology – 2030 Scenario
 Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Acre, Brazil – 2030 Electrification Results by Technology

In the 2030 scenario, grid densification serves approximately 655,000 people (68%), reflecting urban concentration around Rio Branco and other centers. Grid extension reaches roughly 115,000 people (12%), while standalone solar PV serves about 140,000 (15%) and mini-grid PV hybrid systems cover 55,000 (6%).

Total investment for 2030 is approximately USD 513 million, with standalone solar PV requiring the largest share at USD 210 million (41%), followed by grid extension at USD 170 million (33%). Grid densification requires only USD 48 million (9%) despite serving the majority of the population. Total installed capacity is approximately 124.5 MW.

Figure 4
Population Served and Investment Distribution – 2030 Scenario
Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

3.2 Acre – 2050 Scenario

Table 7 presents the results for the 2050 scenario.

Technology	Population 2050	New Conn. 2050	Capacity 2050 (MW)	Investment 2050 (M USD)	Emissions 2050 (tCO ₂)
Grid_dens	782,098	60,544	55.29	95.59	45.41
Grid_ext	150,334	39,216	35.09	204.90	29.10
SA_PV	139,135	43,499	26.03	230.50	0.00
MG_PV_Hybrid	66,431	17,471	49.56	110.16	84.63
MG_Wind	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
MG_Hydro	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Non-electrified	0	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	1,137,998	160,730	165.97	641.15	159.14

Table 7
Summary of 2050 Electrification Results for 3.2 Acre
Note. Values represent exact OnSSET model outputs.

Figure 5 presents the geospatial distribution of electrification technologies across Acre for the 2050 scenario.

Figure 6
 Population, New Connections, Capacity, and Investment by Technology – 2050 Scenario
 Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Acre, Brazil – 2050 Electrification Results by Technology

Under the 2050 scenario, grid densification serves 782,098 people (69%), grid extension 150,334 (13%), standalone solar PV 139,135 (12%), and mini-grid PV hybrid 66,431 (6%). The technology proportions remain stable across both scenarios, indicating a consistent structural pattern in the optimal electrification solution.

Total investment rises to USD 641.15 million, a 25% increase over the 2030 figure. Grid densification doubles from USD 48M to USD 95.59M, while standalone solar PV increases modestly from USD 210M to USD 230.50M. Grid extension grows from USD 170M to USD 204.90M. Total capacity increases from 124.5 MW to 165.97 MW, a 33% growth driven primarily by grid densification and mini-grid expansion.

3.3 Comparison of 2030 and 2050 Scenarios

The following charts compare the two planning horizons, illustrating how investment, capacity, and population will evolve between 2030 and 2050.

Figure 7: Total Investment and Installed Capacity: 2030 vs. 2050
Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Total investment increases by approximately USD 128 million (25%) between 2030 and 2050, from USD 513M to USD 641M. Installed capacity grew by 41.5 MW (33%), from 124.5 MW to 165.97 MW. The relatively modest investment increase compared to the capacity growth reflects economies of scale and the longer amortization period in the 2050 scenario.

Figure 8 Investment by Technology: 2030 vs. 2050
 Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Grid densification investment nearly doubles (USD 48M to USD 96M), reflecting the additional population growth concentrated in urban areas. Standalone solar PV investment grows more modestly (USD 210M to USD 231M), suggesting that most off-grid solar deployment occurs in the near term. Grid extension increases from USD 170M to USD 205M, while mini-grid hybrid investment grows from USD 85M to USD 110M.

Figure 9 Installed Capacity by Technology: 2030 vs. 2050
 Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Grid densification shows the largest capacity increase (27.5 MW to 55.3 MW), doubling between scenarios. Grid extension grows modestly (27 MW to 35 MW). Standalone solar PV capacity remains nearly flat (26 MW to 26 MW), indicating that the same off-grid population is served in both horizons with similar system sizes. Mini-grid hybrid capacity grows from 44 MW to 49.6 MW.

Figure 10: Population Served by Technology: 2030 vs. 2050. Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Figure 11
CO₂ Emissions by Technology: 2030 vs. 2050
Note. Generated from OnSSET model outputs.

Total emissions increase from approximately 109 tCO₂ to 159 tCO₂ between scenarios, a 46% increase driven primarily by mini-grid hybrid systems (which include a diesel component capped at 25%) and the expanded grid serving more connections. Standalone solar PV maintains zero direct emissions in both scenarios.

4. Discussion

The comparison between the 2030 and 2050 scenarios yields several insights for energy planning in Acre. The technology mix remains stable across both horizons, with grid densification consistently serving 68–69% of the population and off-grid solutions serving the remainder. This structural stability suggests that the fundamental geography-driven electrification pattern is established early and maintained as population grows.

A key finding is that standalone solar PV capacity remains nearly unchanged between 2030 and 2050 (~26 MW in both cases), indicating that the dispersed rural population requiring off-grid solutions is already identified and served in the near-term scenario. The additional population growth between 2030 and 2050 is primarily absorbed by grid-connected solutions, which benefit from economies of scale.

The investment analysis shows that approximately 80% of total 2050 investment (USD 513M of USD 641M) is already required by 2030, meaning that the majority of electrification spending is front-loaded. The additional USD 128M between 2030 and 2050 primarily supports grid densification for population growth in urban areas.

The absence of wind and hydro mini-grids in both scenarios reflects the cost parameters used: hydro at 12,000 USD/kW and wind at 1,800 USD/kW cannot compete with solar PV at 950 USD/kW in a region with strong solar irradiance. Future work could explore sensitivity analyses to determine at what cost thresholds these technologies become viable, particularly given Acre's extensive river network which could support small-scale hydro.

The differentiated demand tiers significantly shape the results. Urban Tier 5 demand (3,000 kWh/hh/year) drives grid infrastructure investment, while the lower rural tiers (73–365 kWh/hh/year) make off-grid solutions economically viable. The 18% discount rate applied to standalone systems reflects higher perceived risk but also inflates the apparent cost of solar home systems.

These findings carry direct policy implications for Acre and similar Amazon states. First, the front-loaded investment profile with 80% of costs required by 2030 argues for early mobilization of financing rather than incremental spending. Second, the dominance of standalone solar PV in off-grid areas aligns with the operational model of Mais Luz para Amazônia, which deploys decentralized photovoltaic systems in remote communities. Third, the grid densification pathway depends on the condition and capacity of existing SIN infrastructure in Acre; delays in grid maintenance or capacity upgrades could shift the optimal mix toward more costly off-grid solutions. Finally, the model results support targeted deployment of hybrid mini-grids in medium-density settlements along river corridors, where populations are concentrated enough to justify shared infrastructure but too remote for grid extension.

5. Conclusion

LCoE-based planning using OnSSET provides an efficient electrification strategy for Acre by selecting the least-cost option for each settlement. The two-horizon analysis indicates the following:

Achieving universal access by 2030 requires approximately USD 513 million for 124.5 MW of installed capacity, serving a projected population of 965,000. Extending the horizon to 2050 requires USD 641 million for 166 MW serving 1,138,000 people a 25% investment increase for 18% additional population.

The technology mix is structurally stable: grid densification serves ~69% of the population at ~15% of total cost, while off-grid solar solutions serve the dispersed remainder at higher per-capita cost. Solar-based technologies dominate off-grid electrification; wind and hydro mini-grids are not cost-competitive under current parameter assumptions.

Total CO₂ emissions are minimal (109-159 tCO₂), confirming the low-carbon nature of the electrification strategy. Strengthening grid infrastructure in accessible areas while deploying decentralized solar solutions in remote Amazonian zones, aligned with the region's abundant solar resource, is essential for achieving universal energy access.

6. Limitations and Future Work

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The 2030 scenario values are approximate, derived from model output charts rather than exact tabular outputs; the corresponding emissions estimates are pending verification. The OnSSET model relies on assumptions regarding population projections, demand growth, technology costs, and discount rates that may not reflect actual future conditions. Data on Acre's existing grid infrastructure, particularly medium-voltage network coverage and transformer locations, may be incomplete or outdated, potentially affecting the accuracy of grid extension cost estimates.

The computational constraint that limited this analysis to a single state rather than all of Brazil means that cross-border grid synergies and national-level investment priorities are not captured. The model also does not account for seasonal variability in solar irradiance due to cloud cover during the rainy season, which could affect the reliability and sizing of standalone PV and mini-grid systems in practice.

Future research should address the following priorities: (1) obtaining exact 2030 model outputs including emissions data; (2) conducting sensitivity analyses on key parameters such as discount rates, hydro capital costs, and demand tier assumptions; (3) integrating energy storage modeling to assess battery requirements for off-grid reliability; (4) extending the analysis to neighboring Amazon states for regional comparison; (5) incorporating updated GIS data on Acre's grid infrastructure from ANEEL and EPE; and (6) evaluating the socioeconomic impacts of electrification on health, education, and income outcomes in newly served communities.

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